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Rethinking the Core of the City: beyond functionalism in the Hiroshima Peace Center by Kenzo Tange

Introduction

The evidence which I have based is the articles and illustrations in the Japanese architectural journal; *Shin-kenchiku* (New Architecture) and *Kokusai-kenchiku* (International Architecture). These were published after the CIAM 8 Congress as reports, and simultaneously completing the Peace Center in January 1955.

Those materials of were recorded as the first documents for the CIAM activities by Japanese architects. Therefore, this investigation should imply the historiographical signification of modern movement in Japan concerning to the CIAM.

First attendance to the CIAM

According to the articles relating to the CIAM 8 Congress in the architectural journals in Japan, three architects, Kunio Mayekawa (1905-1986), Kenzo Tange (1913-) and Takamasa Yoshizaka (1917-1980) attended to the congress. The former two architects were as representative of the CIAM Japan, and Yoshizaka as an observer from France during when he had worked at the atelier of Le Corbusier. Mayekawa had actually participated to the CIAM 2 Congress in 1929 to propose a minimum dwelling with Le Corbusier. CIAM 8 was the second time for him to experience the CIAM Congress and to meet European modernists.

The attendance to the CIAM 8 was, however, the first chance for Japanese architects to introduce their

works to the international domain. The speech concerning to the main theme; The Core of the City was done by Tange with referring to a topic with which his Hiroshima plan was intimately related.

Peace Center as beyond functionalism

Tange's presentation, even though a difficult of language, succeeded to show not only the central urban issue of the modern movement based on CIAM principles, like that of the Athens Charter, but also highlight philosophical and architectural differences between Europe and Japan.

Hiroshima Peace Center was initially planned in 1949 as a national-wide competition to create a memorial in remembrance of 200,000 victims of the A-bomb. Tange proposed a long, rectangular history museum raised on piers, with a central view along the axis connecting the plaza, monument, and atomic-bomb dome (World Heritage). Planned to create a close relationship between buildings and the environmental landscape, this project was designed to commemorate the importance of peace and to stop war.

Tange named the axis of the plan "Axis for Prayer" and he believed that the concept could associate between reality and vision of functionalism for cities to satisfy four needs; residence, work, recreation and transportation, in the same point which Team X criticized to the CIAM old generation afterwards.

Tange contributed an article to the *Kokusai-kenchiku* (International Architecture, 10, 1951) as a report of the CIAM 8 Congress entitled "European Homesickness". According to the title, Tange seemingly understood the concept of the 'Core' which was resulted from a sort of irritation or homesickness of Europe against the new world, America. Tange also pointed out that European modernism likely tended to be ideological retreat because of lack of their confidence.

Tange, as a result, had proposed and realized a different characteristic of the CIAM's Core, as it were, 'Negative Core (of Void)' did not have closed centrality but was open to landscape with axis to integrate wish in the world for eternal peace.

Towards a Urbanism

The Hiroshima Peace Center could be said to be a starting point for Tange towards developing the idea of the 'Core and Axis' in his subsequent projects for the city halls in the western part of Japan and the Olympic gymnasium in Tokyo in the 1950s and 60s.

Japanese architects were primarily concerned with developing a systematic planning methodology applicable both to building design and construction and to urbanism through the 1960 Tokyo Plan by Tange. Subsequently, the Metabolism movement

came forth in Japan in synch with Archigram's activities in England.

At the same time, Tange devoted much effort to educate young architects like Isozaki and Kurokawa at the University of Tokyo and his own office, as is typical of architect-professor in Japan. Tange was the first architect and educator to introduce the notion of 'Urbanism' and 'Space' in the Japanese architectural discourse both through theory and practice.

For Tange, the consideration of urban scale very well could have been one means of integrating Western and Eastern thought by experiencing the primary international discussion on "The Core" in the CIAM8.

As a supplemental task of the historical investigation, it should necessarily attempt to identify Japanese architects committed to the modern movement of the CIAM before the World War Second and identify what they proposed through the remaining documents. These questions will lead us to a more complete recording the documents of the CIAM, especially in the postwar period.

It is essential that we identify views outside of orthodox European modernism to incorporate the perspectives of South America and Asia including Japan and India. The exploration of Tange's works provide one such lived experience of an architect who sought to form a modern Japanese society.

Fig. 1 – Hiroshima Peace Centre. Ten Years Ceremony for the end of war

Fig. 2 – Hiroshima Peace Centre. Axis for prayer.

Fig. 3 – Initial Plan (Competition) model.

Fig. 4 – Tange's Office. Left to second tange

Fig. 5 – Hiroshima Peace Centre. Presentation board. For CIAM 8.

Fig. 5 – Itsukushima Shrine

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KEYWORDS

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